

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART VII. ON THE IDENTIFICATION OF β -CARYOPHYLLENE

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The importance of the blue nitrosite in the identification of β -caryophyllene has been pointed out and some of its derivatives have been prepared.

The mixture of hydrocarbons, known as the caryophyllenes, occurs quite widely distributed in nature ("Handbuch der Pflanzen-analyse", dritter Band /erste Halfte, spezielle Analyse II, p.604, 1932 Ed.). Deussen (*Annalen*, 1907, **356**, 1) was the first to recognise that the sesquiterpene "caryophyllene" is not a homogeneous substance. A prolonged series of investigations has led Deussen and co-workers (*Annalen*, 1907, **356**, 1; 1908, **359**, 245; 1909, **369**, 51; 1912, **388**, 136; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1911, *ii*, **83**, 483; 1914, **90**, 324; 1926, **114**, 63; 1927, **117**, 273; 1928, **120**, 133; 1929, **122**, 261) to conclude that caryophyllene contains two, and very probably three hydrocarbons, viz., α -caryophyllene, β -caryophyllene and γ -caryophyllene or isocaryophyllene. The work of Ruzicka and Wind (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, **14**, 410) has rendered the homogeneity of γ -caryophyllene, also doubtful.

Only a very partial separation of these sesquiterpenes can be effected by fractional distillation, and the evidence which Deussen has advanced for their individual existence is based on the isolation of a number of crystalline derivatives originating from different hydrocarbons (Deussen, *Annalen*, 1912, **388**, 136).

Of the various derivatives available for the characterisation of β -caryophyllene (Deussen, *loc. cit.* *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1914), the blue nitrosite holds a unique position. The nitrosochloride is not very suitable, since whenever an attempt is made to obtain a nitrosochloride from a hydrocarbon fraction rich in β -caryophyllene, always a mixture of nitrosochlorides is obtained from which the isolation of β -caryophyllene nitrosochloride is very laborious and often fails; in dealing with a mixture of α -caryophyllene and β -caryophyllene, which usually accompany each other, the mere recrystallisation of the crude nitrosochloride leads to the isolation of α -caryophyllene nitrosochloride, even though in the original mixture the β -caryophyllene may be predominating. The caryophyllene dihydrochloride can be obtained from both β - and γ -caryophyllene. It is not clear whether the β -caryophyllene alcohol originates only from β -caryophyllene or can also be obtained from the γ - and α -varieties. In contrast to all this the blue nitrosite is known to originate definitely from β -caryophyllene and can be very easily prepared and purified.

During the identification of β -caryophyllene, isolated from *Hardwickia pinnata* oil, it was observed that the melting point of the blue nitrosite cannot be raised beyond 110°, though Deussen has reported a m.p. of 115° (*Annalen*, 1907, **356**, 13). Since the difference in the m.p. is appreciable, we were, at first inclined to the view that the nitrosite from the *Hardwickia pinnata* oil might be different from β -caryophyllene nitrosite. As a result of further investigations it has become clear that the m.p. 110° is the correct m.p. of β -caryophyllene nitrosite. A sample of β -caryophyllene nitrosite prepared from genuine caryophyllene (B.D.H.) also melted at 110° and the mixed m.p. with the sample prepared from the oil of *H. pinnata* was

undepressed. This has been confirmed by Simonsen* (*private communication*). He has stated that the m.p. of our product (a sample was sent to him) when introduced in a bath at 100° was 112° and that the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample was the same. It has been observed by us also that the m.p. of the nitrosite depends to some extent on the rate of heating. When the temperature is raised rapidly, the substance melts at about 112°, but on raising the temperature of the bath slowly towards the end (the correct procedure for finding out m.p.) the substance always melts at 110°.

Derivatives of the Nitrosite.—Because of the importance of this blue nitrosite in the characterisation and identification of β -caryophyllene, the properties of the nitrosite have been examined. The very high optical rotation of the nitrosite (+1661) is quite characteristic. The nitrosite is not soluble in aqueous alkali, hot or cold, indicating thereby that the nitrosite is a true nitroso compound and does not isomerise to the oxime form. It reacts easily with strong bases to yield characteristic nitrolamines. The *nitrol-piperidide* and *nitrol-benzylamine* have been prepared. The nitrosite easily reacts with *iodine* giving a very characteristic crystalline compound. The *hydrochloride* obtainable by passing hydrochloric acid gas through an ethereal solution of the nitrosite is also a useful derivative. The melting points of these compounds are recorded in the following table.

Compound.	M.p.	M.p. as given in the literature.
Nitrosite	110°	115°*
Nitrolbenzylamine	172-73°	172-73°*
Nitrolpiperidine	156-57°	—
Hydrochloride	138°	137°*, 140°†
"Iodo-nitrosite"	126°	125°†

* Deussen (*Annalen*, 1912, 388, 136).

†† Deussen (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1914, 11, 90, 324)

EXPERIMENTAL

The blue nitrosite was prepared from the β -caryophyllene fraction of *Hardwickia pinnata* oil (Sukh Dev and Ghua, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 263), and was obtained in blue needles, m.p. 110° with effervescence; $[\alpha]_D$, +1600 (c, 1.24% in chloroform).

Nitrolbenzylamine.—To 0.5 g. of nitrosite, benzylamine (1.5 g.) was added. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for one and-a-half hours. The blue colour disappeared and the colorless solution was cooled, when the compound crystallised out. Alcohol (3 c.c.) was added to it and boiled to dissolve the crystals and allowed to crystallise slowly. The product was once recrystallised from alcohol and once from chloroform-alcohol mixture and was obtained as white, silky needles, m.p. 172-73° with previous shrinking.

Nitrolpiperidine.—A mixture of the nitrosite (1.0 g.), piperidine (1.0 g.) and alcohol (10 c.c.) was refluxed for half an hour and allowed to cool. Water was added till a turbidity just appeared. This was again heated to obtain a clear solution and allowed to

* The authors' sincere thanks are due to Prof. J. L. Simonsen, F. R. S. for taking a mixed m. p. of their nitrosite with his own sample.

crystallise slowly. The product was recrystallised from alcohol several times till the m.p. became constant. It was obtained as white, prismatic needles, m.p. 156-57° (the m.p. depends on the rate of heating, by quick heating it melts above 158° while by slow heating, below 155°). (Found : N, 8.6. $C_{20}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent).

Nitrosite Hydrochloride.—The blue nitrosite (1.0 g.) was dissolved in dry ether (7 c.c.). The solution was chilled to -20° and saturated with a rapid current of dry hydrochloric acid gas. The hydrochloride started separating out towards the end. The bluish green reaction mixture was worked up by removing the solvent and the excess gas in vacuum in a minute current of dry air. The residue was recrystallised from ethyl acetate till the m.p. became constant (two crystallisations). The product was obtained as blue needles, m.p. 138° with effervescence, yield 80%.

"Ido-nitrosite".—The nitrosite (1.4 g., 0.05M) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of chloroform and iodine (0.5 g., 0.041 atom eq.) dissolved in warm chloroform (15 c.c.) was introduced in three lots to the nitrosite solution with shaking. The mixture was then allowed to remain at room temperature with occasional shaking. The iodine colour was slowly discharged and when the colour had faded out to a pale brown (four hours), the solution was poured in a dish and the solvent allowed to evaporate during several hours. The residue on trituration with a little ethyl acetate became solid. It was recrystallised from ethyl acetate (5 c.c.). The product was obtained as stout, transparent, hexagonal prisms, yield 1.0 g., m.p. 126°, (these can be obtained several cm. long and several mm. thick by slow crystallisation), orange-red in colour (the colour depends on the size of the crystals, by quick crystallisation, small, practically colorless crystals can be obtained. The large red crystals give a practically white powder on crushing).

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